

Siitonen, V., Ritonummi, S., Salo, M., Pirkkalainen, H., Mauno, S. (2024). Coping with Technostress in the Software Industry: Coping Strategies and Factors Underlying their Selection (Online Replication Package) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14180104>

Coping strategy (code label)	Code description	Code example	The most common words related to the CS in our data*	Code (label or description) informed by prior research¹
<i>Temporary disengagement from IT use</i>	IT users taking short breaks and temporarily stepping away from stressful IT use incidents.	“I took a break (from technology use) and a moment outside.”	1. Break 2. Take 3. (From) work 4. Relax 5. Rest	Label and description - Salo et al., 2017
<i>Behavioral disengagement (from IT use)</i>	IT users engaging in other activities, such as playing sports or video games to disengage from stressful IT use incidents.	“I just spent time playing video games.”	1. Walk 2. Go/went 3. (Do) something (else) 4. Play 5. Music	Label - Gaudioso et al., 2017 - Russo et al., 2021
<i>Cognitive disengagement (from IT use)</i>	IT users' attempts of actively avoiding thinking about or trying to forget stressful incidents caused by IT use.	“On my free time, I tried actively not to think about the experience.”	1. (Not) think 2. Try 3. Work 4. Concentrate (on something else) 5. Mind	Description Salo et al., 2017
<i>Substance use</i>	IT users consuming substances, such as alcohol or drugs to escape or manage the discomfort caused by stressful IT use incidents.	“I drank a bit more on weekends just to forget.”	1. Smoke 2. Drink 3. Forget 4. Medication 5. Weekend	Label - Newman et al., 2023 - Russo et al., 2021 - Weerasekara et al., 2022
<i>IT avoidance</i>	IT users actively avoiding and refusing to use IT that cause stressful incidents.	“We banned (the use of) that piece of software.”	1. Technology 2. (Not) use 3. Software 4. Try 5. Avoid	Description - Zhao et al., 2020

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<i>Changing jobs</i>	IT users changing jobs to avoid stressful IT use incidents.	"I left the agency and found a new client."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. New 2. Job 3. Change 4. Client/company 5. Find 	Description - Fuglseth & Sørenbø, 2014
<i>Adjusting IT use routines or habits</i>	IT users modifying or changing IT use practices that they find are causing stressful IT use incidents.	"Be mindful of ad hoc calls on communication software, prepare myself for work hours, and not multitask."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Manage 2. Time 3. Development 4. Software 5. Task 	Label and description - Salo et al., 2017, 2020
<i>Fixing the IT</i>	IT users attempts to repair or fix the problem(s) with the IT causing stressful IT use incidents.	"I helped figure out what the problem was and figure out a way to get it fixed."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fix 2. Issue 3. Find 4. Solution 5. Problem 	Label and description - Salo et al., 2020
<i>Using workarounds</i>	IT users coming up with alternate ways and solutions to getting around the IT problem causing stressful IT use incidents.	"I implemented my own manual system until the new one was amended and up to scratch."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Workaround 2. Find 3. Use 4. Alternative 5. Solution 	Description - Salo et al., 2020
<i>IT switching</i>	IT users shifting to a different, more efficient or less stressful, IT and replacing the current one with a substitute.	"We simply ditched that software and moved to its SDK version."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Use 2. Software 3. Alternative/another 4. Change 5. Better 	Label and description - Salo et al., 2020
<i>Planning and strategizing</i>	IT users preparing and planning their courses of actions based on their prior knowledge, expertise, and experiences when faced with potentially stressful incidents with IT use.	"I wrote a sheet of paper with the steps I have to take into account when working with that software. I read the paper before to have these concerns 'fresh' in my mind"	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Time 2. Plan 3. Issue 4. Step 5. Document 	Label - Gaudioso et al., 2017 - Russo et al., 2021

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<i>Asking for technical support</i>	IT users requesting technical support to understand and/or fix the IT problem causing stressful IT use incidents.	"I asked colleagues for help to master my way around the interface."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ask 2. Help 3. Team 4. Contact 5. Support 	Description - Ebert et al., 2019 - Gaudioso et al., 2017 - Zhao et al., 2020
<i>IT use training</i>	IT users engaging in acquiring knowledge and skills through self-learning or formal training to solve stressful IT use incidents.	"I had to learn all the procedures (to use that software) on my own."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Learn 2. New 3. Software 4. Read 5. Search 	Description - Ebert et al., 2019 - Tarafdar et al., 2020
<i>Giving up</i>	IT users engaging in hopeless or helpless thinking and behavior and running out of resources when facing stressful IT use incidents.	"I didn't have any chance (time) for that (to cope)."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unfortunate(ly) 2. (No) chance 3. Nothing 4. Can (not) 5. Resolve/reduce 	
<i>Comfort or contact seeking</i>	IT users seeking social and emotional support from others (e.g., peers, friends, or family) to manage and discuss stressful IT use incidents.	"I discussed the issues themselves with peers, but also engaged in informal conversations."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Talk 2. Colleague 3. Help 4. Team 5. Manager/superior/boss 	Label - Russo et al., 2021 - Weerasekara et al., 2022
<i>Social escape</i>	IT users disengaging from stressful IT use incidents by engaging in unrelated activities and discussions with others.	"We were sending some memes (with my colleagues) so that made the experience a little bit less stressful."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chat/talk/discuss 2. Coworker 3. Break 4. Breather 5. Casual 	
<i>Therapy</i>	IT users seeking help from mental health professionals to discuss the stressful IT use incidents and find ways for technostress mitigation and coping.	"I'm currently going to therapy once a month."	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Therap(y)ist 2. Go/went 3. Anxiety 	

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<i>Emotion control</i>	IT users managing negative emotions to stay stable and calm when experiencing stressful IT use incidents.	“I did try to stay calm and calm my colleagues down.”	1. (Keep/stay) calm 2. Breath 3. Focus 4. Patient 5. Control	
<i>Positive thinking</i>	IT users maintaining an optimistic mindset to focus on solving the IT problem and avoiding self-doubt when experiencing stressful IT use incidents.	“I usually try to stay positive.”	1. Just 2. Positive 3. Try 4. Stay 5. Control	Label and description - Tarafdar et al., 2020
<i>Meditation/ Mindfulness</i>	IT users using the techniques of mindfulness and meditation to address the emotions, thoughts, and feelings caused by stressful IT use incidents.	“I meditate daily.”	1. Meditate 2. Breath 3. Daily 4. Exercise(s) 5. Home	Label and description - Ioannou et al., 2022
<i>Complaining and venting</i>	IT users expressing their emotions, thoughts, and grievances regarding stressful IT use incidents either alone or with others.	“I joined a session of fellow affected users and moaned about it until we reached catharsis.”	1. Complain/rant 2. (With) team 3. Moan	Label and description - Pirkkalainen et al., 2019 - Salo et al., 2020 - Tarafdar et al., 2020
<i>Compromising with IT</i>	IT users making trade-offs regarding their desired ways of using IT or the IT they use to solve or manage stressful IT incidents and achieve stress relief in the long-term.	“I worked on fixing the mistake ASAP. I found it out on a Sunday night but just worked on it because then I wouldn’t have to stress about it (on Monday).”	1. Work 2. Just 3. Try 4. Stress 5. Reduce	
<i>Persuasion to change IT or IT use practices</i>	IT users advocating for modifications, improvements, or changes regarding the IT used or IT use practices causing stressful IT use incidents.	“I suggested that such work be shared among two developers who regularly integrate their code instead of doing it as one process toward the end.”	1. Manager 2. Explain 3. Communicate 4. Ask 5. Suggest	

<i>Acceptance and toleration of stress-inducing IT</i>	IT users acknowledging and coming to terms with the IT or IT use practices causing stressful IT use incidents.	“Accepted, I couldn’t do much (to a server crash) and just tried to keep on top of what I could.”	1. Work 2. Overtime 3. Reduce 4. Accept 5. (No) change	
<i>Cognitive restructuring</i>	IT users changing their perspective or way of viewing stressful IT use incidents.	“I tried to look at it as a challenge, like a puzzle or a problem, instead of an anxious and complex task.”	1. Think(ing) 2. Try 3. Change 4. Technology 5. Approach	Description - Pirkkalainen et al., 2019 - Taipalus et al., 2020
<i>Blaming others</i>	IT users blaming others for causing stressful IT use incidents.	“Started thinking it wasn’t my problem if seniors weren’t interested in helping me.”	1. Manager/senior 2. Developer/team 3. Supplier 4. Know (anything) 5. Fault	
<i>Blaming IT</i>	IT users blaming the IT for causing stressful IT use incidents.	“I decided that it’s not the lack of my own expertise but that the operating system is not intended for software development.”	1. Fault 2. Software 3. Issue 4. Frustration 5. Poor/mediocre	Label and description - Salo et al., 2020

* Word listings drawn from data segments marked as coping effort descriptions. All descriptions coded to represent the same coping strategy were grouped together and analyzed for word frequencies. Common words with minimal semantic value, such as articles and conjunctions, were excluded from the final listings. Only three words listed under the coping strategies “therapy” and “complaining and venting” due to a lack of unique or frequently recurring words.

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